

NEW MEDIA AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION AMONG THE ELDERLY POPULATION IN SOUTHEAST NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16323329>

Abstract: *This study explores the level of awareness and perception of new media technologies among the elderly population in Southeast Nigeria, a demographic often excluded from the rapidly evolving digital landscape. Despite the widespread proliferation of new media, most existing research has focused on younger, tech-savvy users, leaving a critical knowledge gap regarding how older adults engage with digital technologies. This study seeks to fill that gap by examining the demographic factors influencing elderly individuals' awareness and perception of new media. Using a mixed-methods research design, data were gathered from 391 elderly respondents aged 65 and above across five south-eastern Nigerian states. Quantitative data were collected through structured questionnaires, while qualitative insights were obtained via focus group discussions. The analysis focused on respondents' knowledge of digital platforms, perceived ease of use, and perceived usefulness of new media tools such as social media, mobile apps, and internet-based communication platforms. Findings reveal a relatively high level of awareness of new media, especially platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp, and online news services. However, awareness was uneven, with lower recognition of platforms like Twitter, email, and digital apps. Perception of new media was mixed: while a majority acknowledged its usefulness in staying informed and connected, many expressed concerns about complexity, privacy, and usability. Only 36.8% of the respondents found new media easy to use, while 63.2% reported difficulty. The study concludes that although awareness of new media among the elderly is growing, significant barriers in perception persist, influenced by digital literacy, age, and socio-economic background. It recommends targeted digital literacy programmes tailored to the elderly to enhance inclusion and bridge the digital divide.*

Keywords: New media, awareness, perception, elderly, Southeast Nigeria, digital divide, social inclusion.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

The transformation of communication technologies has led to the widespread integration of new media into everyday life. These new media digitally powered platforms including the Internet, social media, blogs, streaming services, and mobile applications have redefined how individuals interact, share

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information, and engage with the world (Flew, 2002; McQuail, 2005). As these technologies become more pervasive, their adoption across different demographic groups has generated significant scholarly interest, especially in terms of awareness and perception.

Before the advent of new media in Southeast Nigeria, communication was predominantly reliant on traditional methods such as the town crier, community meetings, cooperative societies, and various informal social networks like market associations and religious groups (Ogwezzy, 1999; Akpabio, 2003). With the introduction of radio, television, and later digital media, these forms of communication began to decline in relevance. Scholars such as Asogwa (2018) and Nzeji (2019) noted that mass media radio and television ushered in an era of more structured and accessible communication, widely embraced in the southeastern region.

The current wave of digitisation defined as the conversion of analog information into digital formats has catalysed the emergence of new media technologies. These technologies are characterised by convergence, interactivity, immediacy, and vast data storage capacity (Owuamalam, 2008; Obajuluwa et al., 2019). Platforms such as social media networks, online news portals, video-on-demand, and mobile apps exemplify how new media have replaced older technologies like videocassettes and DVDs. The ability to consume, produce, and distribute content simultaneously has created a participatory communication culture (Pringle & Starr, 2013; Schuurman et al., 2015).

Despite the overall expansion of new media in Nigeria where over 50 million people use internet-enabled devices (NCC, 2020; ITU, 2019) studies have largely centred on young, digitally active individuals (Coboh, 2015; Ekeh & Mboso, 2019). In contrast, elderly individuals, defined in this context as those aged 65 and above, remain understudied in terms of their awareness and perception of new media platforms.

Elderly individuals face unique challenges in adapting to emerging technologies. Factors such as limited digital literacy, declining cognitive agility, and entrenched preferences for traditional communication methods can affect their engagement with new media (Edewor, 2016; Zou & Zhou, 2014). Nonetheless, these technologies hold significant potential to improve the quality of life for the elderly, especially in areas such as healthcare information access, social connection, financial services, and public information updates (Ezeah et al., 2013).

In Southeast Nigeria, where elderly persons are increasingly being left out of the digital transformation sweeping across communities, it becomes crucial to examine how aware they are of new media platforms and how they perceive their relevance. Awareness refers not just to knowledge of the existence of these platforms, but also to an understanding of their utility, accessibility, and relevance to daily life. Perception, on the other hand, encapsulates the attitudes, beliefs, and assumptions held

by elderly individuals regarding the usefulness and ease of use of new media (Ugorji, 2019; Hanusch, 2013).

Understanding awareness and perception of new media among the elderly population is particularly critical in a region where digital inclusion is essential to equitable development. Scholars like Edewor et al. (2016) argue that groups that lack awareness or favourable perceptions of new media are at risk of exclusion in today's information society. Bridging this gap can enhance participation, promote autonomy, and support the well-being of older adults in an increasingly digital world. Given the paucity of research targeting this demographic, this study specifically explores the level of awareness and the perception of elderly individuals in Southeast Nigeria concerning new media, with a particular focus on how demographic factors such as age, gender, educational attainment, and income may influence these dimensions.

1.2 Statement of Problem

New media technologies are reshaping communication, access to services, and social engagement across the world. In this evolving digital landscape, it is imperative that all demographic groups, including the elderly, are not left behind. Elderly individuals in Southeast Nigeria stand to benefit immensely from new media platforms in areas such as health information, social connection, and access to public services. However, for these benefits to be realised, there must first be adequate awareness of these technologies and a positive perception of their usefulness and relevance. Without these foundational elements, digital inclusion for this group remains far-fetched.

Despite the widespread availability of new media tools and increasing internet penetration in Nigeria, it is unclear how aware elderly individuals in Southeast Nigeria are of these technologies. It is also uncertain how they perceive new media—whether as useful, intimidating, unnecessary, or beneficial. Demographic factors such as age, gender, level of education, and income may influence both their level of awareness and how they interpret the value of new media in their lives. These variations in awareness and perception may contribute to an underutilisation of digital platforms by the elderly, further widening the generational digital gap.

The gap in knowledge regarding how the elderly understand and respond to new media raises fundamental concerns about their inclusion in a digital society. If awareness is low and perception is negative, then interventions aimed at improving digital access and literacy may not achieve their intended goals. It is therefore essential to investigate the level of awareness and the perception of new media among elderly individuals in Southeast Nigeria, with a focus on how demographic factors shape these experiences. Understanding these dimensions is critical to ensuring that the digital age accommodates the needs of all age groups, including the ageing population.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The general purpose of this study is to ascertain new media awareness and perception among the elderly population in southeast Nigeria. Specifically, the study was guided by the following objective:

1. To examine the level of awareness among elderly individuals based on demographics in Southeast Nigeria regarding new media.
2. To examine the perception of elderly individuals based on demographics in Southeast Nigeria towards new media.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to address the above objectives of study:

1. What is the level of awareness among elderly individuals based on demographics in Southeast Nigeria regarding new media?
2. What is the perception of elderly individuals based on demographics in Southeast Nigeria towards new media?

1.5. Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in this study:

H₁₁: There is significant level of awareness among elderly individuals based on demographics in Southeast Nigeria regarding new media.

H₀₁: There is insignificant level of awareness among elderly individuals based on demographics in Southeast Nigeria regarding new media.

H₁₂: There is positive perception of elderly individuals based on demographics in Southeast Nigeria towards new media.

H₀₂: There is negative perception of elderly individuals based on demographics in Southeast Nigeria towards new media.

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 New Media

New media refers to the digital and computer-based communication technologies that enable the creation, distribution, and consumption of content across various platforms. These include social media, blogs, websites, mobile applications, video-sharing platforms, and online news outlets. Unlike traditional (or "old") media such as radio, television, and newspapers, new media technologies are marked by their interactivity, user-generated content, convergence of media forms, and accessibility across multiple devices (Lister et al., 2021; Asemah, 2011). This transformation has reshaped how information is disseminated and consumed, allowing individuals to both produce and receive content with unprecedented ease.

One defining characteristic of new media is its digital foundation. Information is encoded into bits that allow for rapid transmission, storage, and retrieval, making media consumption more immediate and participatory. This digitisation process has led to the emergence of platforms where communication is no longer one-way but rather multidirectional, enabling greater engagement among users (McQuail, 2005; Owuamalam, 2008). These platforms have evolved into essential tools for personal communication, professional engagement, civic participation, and entertainment.

In the Nigerian context, the use of new media has experienced exponential growth due to increased internet penetration, mobile phone usage, and broader access to digital infrastructure. Reports show that over 50 million Nigerians use internet-enabled devices, positioning the country as a leading digital market in West Africa (ITU, 2019; NCC, 2020). The convergence of media forms such as the blending of text, audio, video, and graphics into single applications has further amplified the appeal and utility of new media in everyday life. However, while adoption rates are high among youths and working adults, the level of adoption among older populations remains uneven.

2.1.2 Awareness

Awareness, in the context of new media, refers to the extent to which individuals recognise the existence of new media technologies, understand their basic functions, and are conscious of their potential uses in daily life. It is the first step in the technology adoption process and forms the foundation upon which further engagement such as perception, trial, or full utilisation is built. Awareness can stem from personal experience, interpersonal influence, formal education, or exposure through mass communication channels.

New media awareness is often shaped by demographic variables such as age, gender, education, and socio-economic status. Individuals with higher levels of education or those belonging to younger age groups are typically more exposed to digital environments and therefore more likely to be aware of evolving media technologies (Schuurman et al., 2015; Edewor et al., 2016). On the other hand, elderly individuals may be less familiar with the functionalities of internet-enabled tools such as smartphones, blogs, or streaming platforms, largely due to generational gaps in digital exposure and usage.

In Southeast Nigeria, traditional forms of communication such as the town crier, market associations, and religious gatherings have historically played a dominant role in information dissemination (Ogwezzy, 1999; Akpabio, 2003). While these methods remain influential among older adults, they do not typically foster awareness of digital technologies. Consequently, many elderly persons may remain unaware of the full range of services, tools, or conveniences that new media can offer such as access to health updates, financial services, or social connectivity. Even when exposure occurs, the absence of digital literacy or supportive infrastructure may hinder full recognition of the media's functions and benefits. Understanding the level of awareness among the elderly is essential, as it is a prerequisite for

perception and eventual adoption. Without adequate awareness, even the most user-friendly digital platforms may remain underutilised by this demographic group.

2.1.3 Perception

Perception, in the context of new media, refers to how individuals interpret, evaluate, and form attitudes toward digital technologies. It encompasses their beliefs about the usefulness, ease of use, relevance, and reliability of these technologies in their everyday lives. Perception plays a crucial role in determining whether an individual progresses from mere awareness to actual adoption and usage of new media tools.

Among the elderly population, perception of new media is often influenced by their prior experience with technology, cognitive comfort, and the perceived value the technology adds to their lives. For many older adults, new media technologies can be seen as complex, overwhelming, or even irrelevant, especially when such platforms are heavily associated with younger generations or entertainment-driven content (Ugorji, 2019). However, for others—particularly those with supportive social environments or higher education—new media may be perceived positively as useful tools for staying informed, connected, and engaged in modern society (Hanusch, 2013).

Negative perception among older adults may stem from fear of the unknown, low digital confidence, or previous difficulties in navigating technology. Additionally, cultural beliefs and lifestyle habits formed in pre-digital eras can shape scepticism toward these rapidly evolving platforms. In Southeast Nigeria, where oral tradition and communal interaction have long served as dominant communication models, many elderly individuals may view digital alternatives as impersonal or unnecessary (Obajuluwa et al., 2019).

Nevertheless, perception is not fixed and can be reshaped through targeted interventions, such as digital literacy training, peer support, and exposure to platforms designed with older users in mind. Understanding how the elderly perceive new media is essential for designing inclusive policies and platforms that align with their needs, capacities, and expectations. A positive perception often precedes adoption and sustained engagement, making it a vital component in efforts to promote digital inclusion among ageing populations.

2.1.4 New Media Awareness and Perception Among the Elderly

The intersection of awareness and perception is particularly important when examining new media engagement among the elderly. While younger populations in Nigeria and globally are widely documented as digital natives, older adults are often described as digitally marginalised. This is especially true in developing regions like Southeast Nigeria, where elderly individuals due to generational, educational, and infrastructural gaps may have limited awareness of, and mixed

perceptions about, the relevance and usability of new media technologies (Edewor, 2016; Schuurman et al., 2015).

In Southeast Nigeria, many elderly individuals continue to rely heavily on traditional channels such as community meetings, religious gatherings, and face-to-face conversations for information and interaction (Ogwezzy, 1999; Akpabio, 2003). These modes, while culturally rooted and still effective, do not expose older populations to digital alternatives. Consequently, awareness of new media platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook, or online news portals tends to be low or superficial. Even when awareness exists, perception is not always favourable, as new media may be viewed as too complex, irrelevant, or tailored to younger users.

Nonetheless, not all elderly individuals resist or dismiss new media. Some, especially those with higher levels of education, greater income, or support from family members, report higher levels of awareness and more positive perceptions of digital platforms. These individuals often use new media for purposes such as maintaining contact with children, accessing health-related information, or following religious and political news. Yet, the variation in engagement levels suggests that demographic characteristics significantly influence both awareness and perception within this age group (Ezeah et al., 2013; Ugorji, 2019).

As society increasingly shifts toward digital platforms for essential services and communication, the need to understand and address the digital awareness and perception gap among the elderly becomes more urgent. Failure to do so could deepen social exclusion and limit the ability of older adults to benefit from resources now predominantly available online. Research focusing on this intersection particularly within culturally distinct regions like Southeast Nigeria is therefore vital for promoting digital inclusivity and intergenerational equity.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) developed by Fred Davis in 1986. TAM provides a robust framework for understanding how individuals come to accept and use a particular technology. The theory posits that two primary factors Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) determine an individual's attitude toward adopting a new technology, which subsequently influences their actual usage behaviour.

Perceived Usefulness refers to the degree to which a person believes that using a particular technology will enhance their performance or quality of life. Perceived Ease of Use, on the other hand, relates to the degree to which a person believes that using the technology will be free from effort. These two variables influence the individual's attitude toward using the technology, which then affects their behavioural intention to use it and ultimately results in actual usage.

The TAM framework is particularly suitable for this study because it directly addresses the two core variables under investigation awareness and perception in relation to new media. Awareness can be seen as a precursor to the development of both perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. That is, if elderly individuals are not aware of a particular new media platform, they are unlikely to form opinions about its benefits or usability. Similarly, perception aligns with how elderly users interpret the utility and complexity of new media technologies. A favourable perception—where the media is seen as beneficial and manageable—may lead to higher likelihood of adoption and use.

In the context of Southeast Nigeria’s elderly population, the TAM helps explain why awareness and perception vary across demographic lines. Factors such as age, education level, income, and prior exposure to technology may all shape the perceived usefulness and ease of use of new media. By applying this model, the study provides a theoretical lens through which to explore the psychological and behavioural mechanisms that influence how elderly individuals respond to digital technologies.

2.3 Empirical Review

Studies have been conducted to explore individual’s perception of new media. One of such studies as conducted by Hanusch (2013) explored the perception of new media among young journalists. The study found that a large percentage of the respondents perceive new media as useful, believing the ability to use new technologies on the job is an important factor that underpin how they approach their tasks and the skills that would be required in journalists of the 21st century.

Igben and Oronukpo (2022) evaluated the perception of public relations practitioners on the incorporation of new media into the process of promoting good relationships between organizations and strategic publics in Nigeria. Findings show that public relations practitioners of both public and private organizations do perceive the adoption of new media technologies in the performance of their function for the promotion of mutual understanding as supportive to quick and interactive approaches to dissemination of information from organizations to strategic stakeholders and the public.

Ugorji (2019) explored the adoption and perception of social media as a new media tool among teachers aged 30-55 years in Lagos State. Findings from the study showed that the relationships between social media subscriptions, and perceived usefulness of social media for socialising and for communication were positive and statistically significant. Similarly, the relationships between the time spent on social media and perceived usefulness of social media for socializing was found to be positive and statistically significant. According to Ugorji (2019), the results suggest that the pre-service teachers are adopters of social media and perceive the media useful not only for social activities but also for academic purposes. In another Nigerian study, Ciboh (2015) explored social media use among older adult aged 65 and above. Findings from the study showed that older Nigerians’ communication on SNS disposed to

bonding social capital as interactions skew towards family members, close friends and colleagues. Findings from the study also showed that although only about three in ten adults' communication tends towards making new friends on social media, adult Nigerians' social interactions on SNS may yet have positive correlation with bridging social capital and its potential resources

Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative survey research design, which was considered suitable for gathering measurable data on the awareness and perception of new media among elderly individuals. The survey method enabled the researchers to reach a broad and diverse population across multiple locations within Southeast Nigeria and to analyse patterns and relationships based on demographic variables such as age, gender, educational attainment, and income level. The design facilitated the use of structured instruments to elicit responses that could be statistically analysed and generalised to the target population.

The area of study covered the five states that make up Southeast Nigeria: Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo. These states were chosen due to their cultural similarities, relatively high literacy rates, and increasing exposure to digital technologies, albeit unevenly across demographic groups. The population of the study comprised elderly individuals aged 65 years and above residing in both urban and rural areas of these states. This age group was selected because it reflects the official retirement age in Nigeria and represents the demographic most likely to experience the digital divide.

A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to ensure a representative distribution across the five states. The sample size for the study was 400 respondents, determined using the Taro Yamane formula for sample size determination. The sample was proportionally allocated across the states to reflect population density and accessibility. Elderly individuals were selected through a combination of purposive and simple random sampling methods, ensuring that both literate and semi-literate participants were included.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, which was carefully designed to capture information on respondents' awareness of various new media platforms and their perception of these technologies. The questionnaire included both closed-ended and scaled questions to allow for quantitative analysis. To ensure validity, the instrument was subjected to expert review in the field of communication and gerontology. Reliability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, and the instrument was found to have an acceptable reliability coefficient.

The data collected were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), with both descriptive and inferential statistics employed. Frequency tables, percentages, and mean scores were used to describe the level of awareness and perception, while inferential tools such as chi-square and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to examine the influence of demographic variables on the

responses. This analytical approach enabled the researchers to draw meaningful conclusions about patterns and relationships within the data.

Data Presentation and Analysis

4.1.2 Demographic Information

This section presents data on the demographic information of the participants. Data was specifically presented on the respondents’ gender, age bracket, highest educational qualification, and area of residence.

Respondents’ Demographics

Table 1: Gender of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	173	44.0	44.0	44.0
Female	218	56.0	56.0	100.0
Total	391	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Age of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
60-65 years	211	54.0	54.0	54.0
66 years and above	180	46.0	46.0	100.0
Total	391	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Educational Qualification of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
First School Leaving Certificate	54	13.8	13.8	13.8
SSCE/Equivalent	104	26.6	26.6	40.4
NCE/OND	79	20.2	20.2	60.6
First Degree/Diploma	100	25.6	25.6	86.2
Postgraduate degrees	54	13.8	13.8	100.0
Total	391	100.0	100.0	

Table 4: Area of Residence of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Rural area	272	69.5	69.5	69.5
Urban area	119	30.5	30.5	100.0
Total	391	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 one above presents data on the respondents' demographic information. As shown in the table, 44.0% (n=173) of the respondents were males, while 56.0% (n=218) were females. This shows a greater proportion of females and males and suggests that there are more older females in south east Nigeria than males.

The table also shows that 53.4% (n=211) of the respondents fell within the age bracket of 60-65, while 47.0% (n=180) fell within the age bracket of 66 years and above. The results on the respondent' age suggests that there are more elderly persons aged 60-65 years than there are those aged 66 years and above in southeast, Nigeria.

Regarding educational qualification, the table shows that 6.1% (n=24) of the respondents have First School Leaving Certificates; 26.5% (n=104) have SSCE/Equivalent; 20.2% (n=79) have NCE/OND certificates; 25.6% (n=100) first degree/diploma, while 13.8% (n=54) had postgraduate degrees. The results on the participants education qualification show that majority of the respondents have basic education.

Regarding the respondents' area of residence, Table 4 shows that 69.5% (n=272) reside in rural areas, while 30.5% (n=119) reside in urban areas. This result suggests that there are more elderly persons living in the rural areas than there are those living in the urban areas in south east Nigeria.

4.1.3 Awareness of new media

This section presented data on the respondents' awareness of new media. The respondents were required to indicate if they were aware of new media or not. In addition, the respondents who indicated that they were aware of new media were asked the extent of their awareness. Also, the category of respondents that indicated that they were aware of new media was asked their extent of awareness of new media, as well as their new media technologies of awareness.

Table 5: Respondents’ awareness of new media

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	298	76.0	76.0	76.0
No	93	24.0	24.0	100.0
Total	391	100.0	100.0	

Chart 1

Table 5 presents data on the respondents’ awareness of new media. Of the 391 respondents, 76.0% (n=298) indicated that there were aware of new media. On the other hand, 24.0% (n=93) indicated that they were not aware of new media. The table shows that majority of the respondent are aware of new media.

Table 6: Respondents’ extent of awareness of new media

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very little extent	82	21.0	21.0	21.0
Little extent	26	6.6	6.6	27.6
Moderate	66	16.9	16.9	44.5
Large extent	108	27.6	27.6	72.1
Very large extent	109	27.9	27.9	100
Total	391	100.0	100.0	

Chart 2

Table 6 presents data on the level of awareness of new media among the respondents who indicated that they were aware of new media. Results presented in the table shows that 27.9% (n=109) of the respondents were aware of new media to a very large extent; 27.8% (n=108) were aware to a large extent; 20.8% (n=62) were aware to a very little extent, while 16.9% (n=66) were aware to a moderate extent. The results also showed that 6.6% (n=26) were aware to a little extent. The results presented on Table 6 suggest that there is an overall high level of awareness of new media among the respondents.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Social media (Facebook, Whatsapp, etc.)	140	35.8	35.8	35.8
Digital/smart television	40	12.2	12.2	48.0
Cable technology	100	25.6	25.6	73.6
Digital cameras	32	8.2	8.2	81.8
Video games	34	8.7	8.7	90.5
Email	25	6.4	6.4	96.9
Mobile application (Apps)	20	5.1	5.1	100

Total	391	100.0	100.0
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Table 7: New media technologies of awareness

Chart 3

The respondents were asked about their new media technologies of awareness. They were allowed to indicate as many new media technologies as applicable. Table 7 shows that 35.8% (n=140) of the respondents were aware of social media; 6.4% (n=25) were aware of email; 5.1% (n=20) were are of other Mobile phone Applications, were aware of digital cameras; 25.6% (n=100) were aware of cable technology, 8.2% (n=32) while 8.7% (n=34) and 8.2% (n=32) were aware of video games and digital/smart television, respectively. Findings presented on Table 7 show significant awareness of new media among the elderly population of southeast with social media having the highest statistical score.

4.1.4 Perception of new media

This section presents the respondents’ views on their perception of new media. The focus was on the perception of ease of use of new media and perception of usefulness of new media.

Table 8: Perception of ease of use of new media

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	144	36.8	36.8	36.8
No	247	63.2	63.2	100.0
Total	391	100.0	100.0	

Chart 4

Table 8 presented data on the participants' ease of use of new media. Results presented on the table shows that 63.2% (n=247) of the respondents were of the perception that new media is not easy to use, while 36.8% (n=144) perceived the use of new media to be easy. The results show that majority of the respondents thought of new media as technologies that are difficult to use. The implication of this result is that many of the respondents would not be able to adopt or utilise the new media.

Table 9: Respondents' responses on the aspects of new media that are easy to use

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Watching online videos	60	15.3	15.3	15.3
Uploading & Downloading Documents	118	30.2	30.2	45.5
Copying & Pasting	17	4.3	4.3	49.8
Transferring of audio files & pictures	196	50.2	50.2	100
Total	391	100.0	100.0	

Chart 5

Table 9 presented respondents' views on the aspect of new media that are easy to use. Results show that 15.3% (n=60) of the respondents indicated that using new media to watch online videos, while 30.2% (n=118) indicated using new media for uploading and downloading documents. In addition, 4.3% (n=17) indicated that it was easy for them to see the new media for copying and pasting files and 50.2% (n=196) indicated that using new media for transferring of audio files and pictures was easy. Findings presented in Table 9 suggest that the respondents who were aware of the new media were able to note various aspects they could perceive as easy-to-use. However, the use of new media to transfer audio files and pictures was predominantly used by respondents.

Table 10: Perception of usefulness of new media

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	267	68.3	68.3	68.3
No	124	31.7	31.7	100.0
Total	391	100.0	100.0	

Chart 6

Table 10 presented data on the respondents’ perception of usefulness of new media. Findings in the table shows that 68.3% (n=267) perceived new media as useful, while 31.7% (n=124) perceived it otherwise. The results show that majority of the respondent perceived new media as useful. The implication of this result is that there is a likelihood that majority of the respondents would use new media technologies considering the fact that they perceive them as useful.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

Four hypotheses were tested using the inferential statistics (Chi-square) to validate or otherwise refute the hypotheses. Chi-square was considered suitable because the data generated from this study confirm to nominal and interval forms.

The formulated hypotheses were rested using the chi-squared goodness of fit. The chi-square formula is given as stated below:

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$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(oi - ei)^2}{ei}$$

Where X^2 = (the Chi-squared symbol)

Σ = Zigma (summation)

oi = observed frequency

ei = expected frequency

Hypothesis One

H₁: There is significant level of awareness among elderly individuals based on demographics in Southeast Nigeria regarding new media.

H₀₁: There is insignificant level of awareness among elderly individuals based on demographics in Southeast Nigeria regarding new media.

To test the above hypothesis, data on Table 6 were used. From the table, a contingency table is shown below:

Table 6: Respondents’ extent of awareness of new media

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very little extent	82	21.0	21.0	21.0
Little extent	26	6.6	6.6	27.6
Moderate	66	16.9	16.9	44.5
Large extent	108	27.6	27.6	72.1
Very large extent	109	27.9	27.9	100
Total	391	100.0	100.0	

Applying Chi-Square:

	oi	ei	oi – ei	(oi – ei) ²	$\frac{(oi - ei)^2}{ei}$
Very little extent	82	98	-16	96	1.0
Little extent	26	98	-72	5184	52.9
Moderate	66	98	-32	1024	10.4
Large extent	108	98	10	100	1.0
Very large extent	109	98	11	121	1.2
Total	391				66.5

Operative Assumptions:

- (1) A level of significance (e) = 0.05
 - (2) Degree of freedom (df) = (C - 1) (5 - 1) = 4
- The table value: 66.5
- The critical value: $\chi^2_{(0.05, 24)} = 9.488$

Decision Rule: Reject H_0 if $\chi^2_{cal} > \chi^2_{(0.05, 28)} = 9.488$ Otherwise do not reject H_0 .

Conclusion: Since the table value (66.5) is greater than the critical value (9.488), the alternate hypothesis that stated that there is significant level of awareness among elderly individuals in Southeast Nigeria regarding new media is accepted.

Hypothesis Two

H_2 : There is positive perception of elderly individuals based on demographics in Southeast Nigeria towards new media.

H_2 : There is negative perception of elderly individuals based on demographics in Southeast Nigeria towards new media.

To test the above hypothesis, data on Table 10 were used. From the table, a contingency table is shown below.

Table 10: Perception of usefulness of new media

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	267	68.3	68.3	68.3
No	124	31.7	31.7	100.0
Total	391	100.0	100.0	

Applying Chi-Square:

	oi	ei	oi - ei	(oi - ei) ²	$\frac{(oi - ei)^2}{e_i}$
Yes	267	196	71	5041	25.7
No	124	196	-72	5184	26.4
Total	391				52.1

Operative Assumptions:

- (1) A level of significance (e) = 0.05
 - (2) Degree of freedom (df) = (C - 1) (2 - 1) = 1
- The table value: 52.1

The critical value: $\chi^2_{(0.05, 24)} = 3.841$

Decision Rule: Reject H_0 if $\chi^2_{cal} > \chi^2_{(0.05, 28)} = 3.841$ Otherwise do not reject H_0 .

Conclusion: Since the table value (52.1) is greater than the critical value (3.841), the alternate hypothesis that stated that there is positive perception of elderly individuals in Southeast Nigeria towards new media is accepted.

5.1 Summary of Findings

Findings from the study showed that majority of the respondents were aware of new media and there is an overall high level of awareness of new media among the respondents. The new media technologies of awareness included social media platforms, email, cable technology, and digital cameras. Furthermore, results showed that majority of the respondents thought of new media as technologies that are difficult to use. The implication of this result is that many of the respondents would not be able to adopt or utilise the new media.

a. There is significant awareness on new media among the elderly in Southeast, Nigeria as affirmed by the findings of Survey and Focus Group Discussion. The study found that the elderly population mainly access social media (Facebook, Whatsapp etc) than other types of new media.

b. On nature of perception about new media, the findings found that elderly population find the news media easy to use and operate. The implication of this result is that there is a likelihood that majority of them use new media technologies considering the fact that they perceive them as useful. As a result, they engage in different online activities such as watching online videos, uploading and downloading documents and transferring of audio files and pictures. However, the findings of Focus Group Discussion found that the elderly population often needs assistance from the younger generations to operate some of these new media.

5.2 Conclusion

This study concludes that there is a disparity between the proportion of elderly persons in Nigeria who are aware of new media and those who utilise it. While a significant portion of the elderly population in Southeast Nigeria is aware of new media many do not utilise it due to lack of exposure, digital literacy barriers, lack of digital skills, fear of technology, concerns about privacy and security, as well as preference for traditional communication methods. The findings reveal the presence of a digital divide among the elderly population, with disparities in access to and utilization of new media. Major socioeconomic factors for this disparity include education and urban-rural divide,

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proffered:

To encourage adoption, it is crucial that Government should design educational programmes that address the concerns of the elderly and emphasize the benefits of new media technologies. These programmes should be accessible on radio, television and social media. The programme should be tailored to the specific needs of the aged population. Developers should consider the unique challenges faced by the elderly when designing new media platforms, focusing on user-friendly interfaces, intuitive navigation, and features that cater to their preferences.

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Michigan International Journal of Marketing, New Media and Communication

Volume 13 Issue 3, July-September 2025

ISSN: 2836-9424

Impact Factor: 6.39

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJMNMC>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Zou, B., & Zhou, M. (2014). Technology use among the elderly: A systematic review. *Journal of Gerontology and Geriatric Research*, 3(1), 1–7.